

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF STITCHED 3D-WOVEN-COMPOSITES/TITANIUM SINGLE-LAP JOINT

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Introduction & Test procedure

- The main aim of this paper is to find out the failure mechanism of three-dimensional-woven-composites/titanium-alloy single-lap joints.
- Specimens with different stitching parameters were tested and a microscope connected with an industrial camera was used to record the performance of the joints and the stitches during the test.
- That performance are used to reveal the failure mechanism of the joint.
- The effect of the stitching parameters on strength of 3D-woven composites/titanium alloy single lap joint is also presented in this research.

Test device and Load/displacement curve

Photos during the test

Result

- Higher stitch density and 48k fiber bundle specification are known can provide larger joint strength.
- During the test, the suddenly decrease of the stiffness of the joint shows some failure happened and the crack initial near the stitches shows there was a stress redistribution. The failure of the composite-titanium interface is a reasonable explanation for this phenomenon.
- Stitching hole diameter can also affect the strength and stiffness of the joint. The stiffness decrease when the hole becomes bigger. However, due to the matrix material in the stitching hole shares part of the shear stress, the strength of the joint remains at a relatively high level until the stitch hole is too large and the stitches lost its effect.

